

SOCIOLOGY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION: DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *The article provides detailed information about the characteristics and research directions of the sociology of preschool education, which is considered a branch of the sociology of education.*

Keywords: *social need, goal, development, innovation, cognitive, development, child personality, humanism, intellect, management, pedagogical process.*

Today's modern society is explained by the activities of people in various associations. In this society, people spend most of their lives in this organized society (organization) as they carry out various activities together depending on their age and activity. Such organizations gather different groups of society according to their activities, organizational management, ethics, culture, planning, i.e. the work and projects carried out in them determine the existence of the organization and its place and essence in the development of society and human life. , which we distinguish based on their naming, purpose of activity, theoretical and methodological foundations.

The periods of human life related to childhood are spent in preschool education. That is why the role and importance of preschool education organization in society and the need of humanity for it are increasing day by day. This organization is a place where children who are just starting their life, ensure their social adaptation to the society and develop their cognitive activity. Analyzing the system of pre-school education, which is considered as the first stage of education, based on a sociological approach, we tried to research it as a part of the sociology of education based on the identification of its specific features. In this, we certainly worked based on the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of the sociology of education. According to L. N. Kogan, the founder of the first interpretation of the object and subject of the sociology of education, educational institutions of various levels work as objects of sociological research. We worked based on the idea that the subject of sociology of education includes the study of the compatibility between education received in an educational institution and social needs. [4]. It is clear from L.Sh. Kogan's thoughts that modern educational organizations can be considered as a mechanism that ensures the development of society and social changes. After all, any progress and changes are related to the progress of science and education, therefore, any innovation in education can be considered as a process of modernization of society. While researching these processes in society, T. Parsons [6] shows three components of this process: democratic, industrial and educational revolutions. The democratic revolution changed the political structure of modern societies, making political governance impersonal, devoid of charismatic elements, based on various electoral procedures called "representative democracy". The Industrial Revolution largely separated the labor sector from the family economy and made it independent, which gave rise to the phenomenon of organization as a way of doing business. The revolution in education played a decisive role in any society, making knowledge the most important factor in production and other areas.

Any changes in society will not fail to have an impact on human life, but man will appear as the main reformer of these changes. Reforms are carried out on the basis of reason and science. That's why he is sought after in the desire to rationally set his goals, to achieve his most important goals, and to find a rational way, at the same time, he adapts the achieved results to his intentions. Undoubtedly, all this is achieved through education and self-development. The importance of this activity is that it gives a person the ability and desire to rationally organize his activities, and encourages him to search for the most reasonable and effective principles of achieving the goal. In society, the educational system, in particular, the pre-school education system and its quality, harmony with the times is a factor of sustainable development. Because the effect of every child's steps in life is directly related to the development of his knowledge and thinking, the stronger the initial foundation of this development, the more he will mature as a person. Russian researcher B. B. Mayer writes about this: "education as a system of cultural reproduction and a system of "cognitive" training of young generations entering social life has always been at the center of the suprabiological evolution of mankind and the development of civilization" [5]. In fact, special attention is paid to the child's education and development in the activities of preschool educational organizations. Observing the dynamics of modern social development today, we can see that a lot of changes have taken place in the preschool education system, which is considered the lower level of education. The fact that this system now works on the basis of a competency-based approach to the education of children creates new phenomena and processes in the field and has led to an increase in the weight of scientific research on solving existing problems in the field. The research and analysis of the achievements and shortcomings of the preschool education system belongs to the sociology of education, and based on the specific characteristics of the field, it has great opportunities for both theoretical and empirical research of this social system.

In this article, we tried to determine the place and role of sociology of preschool education in sociology of education. Because the reforms and scientific research carried out in the preschool education system in the following years are aimed at clarifying the development prospects of the sector, the implementation of the national program aimed at ensuring coherence and continuity in the education system of our country, in the context of the integration of preschool education with other educational stages. it will be important to consider this issue in order to further increase its theoretical and social-practical importance.

In recent years, the direction of a number of scientific works, including the problems of preschool education, has expanded, and the content has also improved. The path of these scientific works includes preschool pedagogy, psychology of preschool children, management of preschool education, marketing of preschool education, sociology of education. It can be seen from the above that the scientific scope of studying preschool education is quite wide and it is important to conduct research in these areas.

Sociology of preschool education is a unique feature of preschool education, first of all, it is manifested in the number of directions of scientific research in the field, the increase in the scope of study and their gradual improvement, and their recognition. It fulfills its task by covering all aspects of the field in a direct and indirect way, and also creates a basis for further improvement of scientific understanding of the field. In addition, sociology also functions as a source of general scientific conceptual apparatus. In addition, there is an increasing number of new aspects of preschool education that can be studied, the fact that the field is establishing its own position in society and manifesting itself as the first stage of education, mainly in terms of ensuring the all-

round development of preschool children, there are a lot of problems that can be studied. part of it is now falling into the educational perspective and is being comprehensively covered. A vivid example of such changes can be the professional standard of educators and the requirements for the quality of education and their fulfillment, or problems related to the management of preschool education organizations, which were initially mainly addressed by pedagogy. Considers educational and educational activities in the context of preparation for implementation. Today, this situation is actively studied by educational sociology (status of educators-pedagogues in society, pedagogical relations, pedagogical process, quality of education), pedagogical psychology: (diagnostics of professional activity, professional skills of pedagogues-educators, preschool age psychological characteristics of children, implementation of inclusive education), management of preschool education (work motivation). The sectoral directions of sociology, including preschool education, are determined by their position as a branch of sociology, the theoretical (conceptual) state and potential of the field, which is directly reflected in the methodological characteristics of the field. These features not only explore the unique aspects of preschool education, but also determine the relationship and boundaries of different areas of education, integration between areas related to the field, and possible theoretical connections. . Therefore, to assess this situation, it is appropriate to consider the methodological foundations of the sociology of preschool education.

The relatively young methodological foundations of the sociology of preschool education include understanding its object, the state of the field of preschool education and the category-conceptual apparatus, general principles of sociological study of preschool education. In this case, the individual elements of the educational system or its social problems. These principles are also noteworthy for their connection with social values. Because sociological principles seek to develop a unique concept of holistic education to overcome the problematic aspects of the field. As a result, the object of study of the sociology of the preschool education system, the educational processes and problems, also determines the cognitive and social practical possibilities of children's development. In the process of studying the methodological principles of the sociology of preschool education, first of all, the child and his socialization are considered as the main factors of the effectiveness of education, and the second is the principle of integrity, which embodies the mutual integration of a number of factors that determine the development of a preschool child. is enough. This principle represents the process of harmonious development of the child as a biosocial and existential being, and provides for the achievement of the unity of all the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the child's creative development: 1) pedagogical process based on the individual-oriented educational technology in the development of each child and designing educational relationships; 2) use of educational methods based on mutual integration in the development of children's intelligence; 3) to use the possibilities of the child's development areas and specific microenvironment, to be able to use modern educational technologies, STEAM technology appropriately to achieve the educational goal.[2]

Implementation of the principle of socialization of the child helps the child adapt to the organization of preschool education and effectively organize the pedagogical process. Both principles used in the research of preschool education serve the development of a child with specific individual characteristics that are the object of educational relations and pedagogical processes. In this case, the nature of the child, his health, physiological, physical, mental and social condition is taken into account. The importance of these principles is that they require compliance

with the conditions that must be followed in any pedagogical process and conditions: 1) strengthening the child's physical and mental health, teaching a healthy lifestyle; 2) looking at the child as an equal member of this process in pedagogical processes, activating him, helping him to self-educate and develop; 3) taking into account the zones of proximal and real development that determine the individual and age capabilities of each child; 4) in the implementation of pedagogical relations: from simple to complex, from ignorance to knowledge. These actions directly correspond to the requirements of the humanitarian principle. It is known from history that humanitarianism reflects social reality "not from the point of view of what is, but from the point of view of what should be," says T. Kaldibaeva.[3] From the point of view of this view, humanitarianism represents the criterion of the level of development of society, and humanitarianism is considered as the most priority direction of values that should be followed in the pedagogical process of preschool education, and compliance with its conditions is also required, in particular: 1) development of pedagogical technologies suitable for the implementation of the social education process based on a differential approach to each child; 2) full recognition of children's rights; 3) to help the child achieve success based on the positive qualities of his personality; 4) targeted implementation of humanitarian education of the participants of the pedagogical process; 5) ensuring proportionality of relations between the participants of the pedagogical process from an ethical and aesthetic point of view.[1] "For this, it is appropriate to work based on universal values, following the rules regulating economic and social transactions, because the preschool education organization is a moral-intellectual field, like all organizations of the spiritual and educational level of society".[7]

It is necessary to emphasize the importance of the constant monitoring of education and training standards that support the comprehensive development of the preschool child for the sociology of the preschool education system. The purpose of this is: based on the study of achievements and shortcomings in the activities of MTTs, it is necessary to effectively organize and manage their activities, and to develop a system for improving the quality of education, involving parents in this process. This organization of work makes it possible to evaluate the quality of educational services on the basis of direct informed management. As a result, the professional competence of teachers-pedagogues increases, a positive approach to their profession is ensured, which in turn creates an environment of transparency in providing quality education to children and comfortable communication with parents. The creation of such an environment develops the child's field competence, as well as develops self-management skills and increases creativity.

To sum up, the sociology of preschool education, which is a branch of the sociology of education, is a number of disciplines close to it in terms of field problems, research methods: pedagogy, educational psychology, necessary meaningful information based on the results achieved in the fields of educational management, embodies methodological tools, theoretical generalizations and serves the development of the preschool education system. Because, in addition to the sociological analysis of the preschool education system of our country, it is necessary to develop the children of the preschool education organization as a well-rounded person in all aspects, to study the existing problems and tasks in the field, the condition of the preschool education institutions in our country today, the preschool education in our country There is a need for a sociological analysis of the activity of the educational institution.[8]

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